

Supplementary table 1. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for germination, speed index, and mean germination time of *J. mollissima* seeds.

Germination (%)					
	GL		F		p-value
Lot	5		2.06		0.002 **
Temperature	1		0.73		0.008 **
Germination Speed Index					
	GL	SS	MS	F	p-value
Lot	5	13.24	2.64	8.04	1.06 ⁻⁰⁵ **
Temperature	1	4.78	4.78	14.52	0.0003 **
Waste	53	17.44	0.32		
Coefficient of Variation (%)		36.86			
Mean Germination Time (days)					
	GL	SS	MS	F	p-value
Lot	5	25.93	5.18	14.62	5.31 ⁻⁰⁹ **
Temperature	1	8.09	8.09	22.81	1.45 ⁻⁰⁶ **
Waste	53	18.79	0.35		
Coefficient of Variation (%)		10.72			

** Significant at 5% significance; SS: Sum of squares; MS: Mean of squares.